

GENDER EQUALITY: IMPACT ON GROWTH AND EDUCATION OF GIRLS AND STRATEGIES TO ENHANCE GENDER EQUALITY

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Abstract:

Gender equality, also known as sexual equality or equality of the sexes, is the state of equal ease of access to resources and opportunities regardless of gender, including economic participation and decision-making; and the state of valuing different behaviors, aspirations and needs equally, regardless of gender. In many empirical and theoretical studies, female to male ratio of education is used as the measure of gender equality that is hypothesized to have an impact on economic growth and development. In this paper includes supporting strategies to enhance **gender** equality in the classroom. Also it discusses how to create a more equal and balanced learning environment. An educated individual is more likely to grow up healthy and have more opportunities for employment. This increases their chance of raising healthy children, and supporting them to also get an education. When all students, both male and female, have equal access to educational opportunities, the results **impact** future generations.

Concept of Gender Equality:

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Impact of gender equality on Growth and Education of Girls

In many empirical and theoretical studies, female to male ratio of education is used as the measure of gender equality that is hypothesized to have an impact on economic growth and development. This is probably partly due to the fact that comparable data on education is one of the only measures available across countries. Education of girls is an important factor in understanding the connections between the status of women, welfare of the family, the human capital available in a society and future development. Many empirical studies conclude that increased schooling of the mother is associated with larger effects on child health, schooling and adult productivity than increased schooling of the father (see Schulz, 2001, for references). Even in the developed world, there is some evidence that the mother's education has a greater impact on children's performance later in life than the father's. At the level of national economy, there is a strong positive correlation between countries' per capita GDP levels and gender equality measured by female to male years of schooling (see Lagerlöf, 2003). Even though it is difficult to identify the nature of the (inter)dependence between these variables empirically, there are good reasons to believe that the actual levels of gender equality are not an outcome of efficient economic choice.

In a growth model, a religious preference not to educate girls leads to a distortion that prevents the efficient accumulation of human capital. Economy-wide gender biases are likely to coexist with market failures, which further contribute to the under-investment in girls. Educational resources will be misallocated. Parents tend not to invest resources in girls when the benefits go to another family or if labor market discrimination, either in the form of lesser salaries or by direct barriers to entry, makes a proper return on their investment unlikely. Esteve-Volart (2000) models labor market discrimination in the form of barriers to entry as a cause of both educational inequality and reduced growth. Gender inequality impacts growth by reducing the pool of talented people whose ideas in turn lead to technological progress. The underlying entrepreneurial talents of men and women are assumed to be evenly and identically distributed.

Discrimination is modeled by excluding women from the managerial positions, allowing them to be only workers. As workers they may choose more primary education to increase their productivity. Any further education does not benefit them because of the exclusion from managerial positions. This form of gender bias leads to a fall in the average talent of managers, who are assumed to be the ones coming up with good or bad ideas. The average quality of ideas in turn determines growth through technological improvements.

The above mentioned realities can be solved by reflecting back to the school and the classrooms. It's important that all class members be given the chance to succeed no matter their gender. You can help achieve gender equality in your classroom by challenging traditional stereotypes and creating equal opportunities for your students. By fostering an inclusive classroom environment, people of all genders will feel welcome and respected. The best educational environments are those that are fair to all students, male or female. But in many places around the world, female and male students do not always have the same chances for a good education.

In this paper we will discuss supporting **gender** equality in the classroom. We also will discuss how to create a more equal and balanced learning environment. An educated individual is more likely to grow up healthy and have more opportunities for employment. This increases their chance of raising healthy children, and supporting them to also get an education. When all students, both male and female, have equal access to educational opportunities, the results **impact** future generations. Creating more equal educational opportunities for students begins in the classroom and with the teacher. A strong teacher is one who treats their students fairly and creates an environment where students feel equally able to take part. These strategies will help teachers create a more equal classroom environment for their students. They will also help teachers effectively manage their classrooms. Remember: The best form of teaching is the fairest form of teaching!

Strategies for enhancing Learning Environments

Teachers can create the appearance of gender **bias** through unintentional, nonverbal actions. The first step to correcting this problem is to organize your classroom in a way that makes all students feel equal.

- Establish rules

It is important for a teacher to establish a set of rules from the very beginning that promote equality. An effective way to do this is to create class rules with students. Ask students to suggest ideas for how to keep an equal and respectful classroom.

This permits the teacher to point to the rules as something that the whole class has agreed on. It is important to include rules that deal with respecting students, respecting the teacher and **participating** in class.

- Have a classroom seating plan that supports equal participation.

If you find that certain students, regardless of their gender, are not participating in class, try to change your class seating plan. For example, try having students who usually sit in the back come to the front.

Teachers **tend** to interact the most with students sitting closest to them. For this reason, it is important to change the seating order (if possible) to give all students a chance to sit near the teacher.

- Have equal academic and behavior expectations for all students

Teachers should try to avoid making things easier for either male or female students by giving them easier questions in class, or trying to solve things for the students.

Doing this can create the **perception** that certain students are not as smart as others. Teachers should hold the same expectations of all students.

- Use group work

Often there will be some students, male or female, who are not comfortable speaking in front of large classes. But, they may feel more comfortable speaking in small groups. In order to give all students the opportunity to take part in class, try doing some activities in small groups of three to four students.

Classroom strategies

After organizing your class in a way that promotes equality, the next step is to consider the effects of your actions in class.

- Addressing students equally

One of the main opportunities students have to participate in class is when they are answering teachers' questions. Teachers need to call on or talk to both female and male students in a balanced way. Research shows that both male and female teachers often call on male students to speak in class more often than female students.

- Provide enough wait time to answer questions.

Some students, male or female, may need time to think about the answer to a question when called on by a teacher. When calling on students who seem to wait longer to answer a question, make sure to give students at least four to five seconds. Research shows that giving students more time to answer will increase the number of students who participate.

- Use gender neutral language

Sometimes in English people use male pronouns when referring to a group. But, this can make female students feel left out. Teachers should use gender **neutral** pronouns whenever possible. One example is, instead of saying "guys" when referring to a class or group (which is common in American English), say "everybody" or "everyone."

- Body language

Teachers may not realize that their body language with female students might be different from what it is with male students.

Whenever male or female students are talking, use respectful, listening body language. Face the listener, do not walk away, and do not interrupt students.

Also the teacher can move to different areas of the classroom while speaking. This is important because students sitting further from the teacher tend to participate less.

- Discipline

Be aware when male students insult female students, or female students insult male students. If the insults appear to be gender-based, students may be discouraged from participating in class in the future. Be quick to intervene and discipline the students making insults. This shows students of either gender that they will be supported. However it is important that both male and female students are given the same **discipline** for the same actions.

These strategies will help teachers create a more equal classroom environment for their students. They will also help teachers effectively manage their classrooms. Remember: The best form of teaching is the fairest form of teaching!

Conclusions:

First, the current situation in many developing countries is strikingly similar to that of Western Europe roughly a hundred years ago. Today's developing nations face the same issues that the now developed countries resolved over the past century or two: education for girls, women's political, legal and marital rights, employment outside of the home for women and men alike, lower fertility and reduced child mortality. The current economics literature reveals that hierarchical (or patriarchal) gender valuations appear in many different guises. Overall the literature hints as to the aspects of gender inequality that seem to be associated with the overall level of economic development: values and religion, cultural restrictions, legal and inheritance laws and practices, the marital pattern of resource allocation, monogamy vs. polygyny, labor market access, education, fertility, gender specific market

failures in finance, and power in political decision making. The challenge in the future may be to look at the issues from men's perspective as well. How does gender inequality adversely affecting men? What are the disadvantages, cultural, and economic restrictions that men face? Those restrictions will be different from the ones women face but they may be even more severe in their own ways. These restrictions and assumptions about men's roles have only recently been questioned, and only in the most technologically-advanced cultures. There cannot be real gender equality unless the road leading to it increases well-being for men as well as women.